

COMPLICATIONS AFTER CAESAREAN SECTION

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There is an increase in caesarean sections (CS) worldwide. In Russia, the current rate of CS is 16%-30%. The increase in CS increases the likelihood of complications developing, which can contribute to reproductive dysfunction in these women.

Target: analysis of the structure and risk factors for the development of complications after CS.

Material and research methods. A retrospective analysis of birth histories using CS. Born in 2012-2022 2312 births were recorded in the department of the Andijan regional perinatal center, of which 28,5%(660) by CS. Emergency CS was performed in 235 women (35%) – 1 gr. 2 gr-425 pregnant women delivered surgically through as planned (65%). Research results. In total, after operative childbirth, 5% complications (n=33). Indications for emergency CS: bleeding (13,6%), onset of labor or premature rupture of amniotic fluid in the presence of a scar on the uterus (23,8%), weakness of labor (46,3%), acute hypoxia fetus (16,2%). In 1 group there were 28 complications (11,9%). Among them: bleeding during surgery due to presentation and rotation placenta – 10,7% (n=3), the presence of multiple uterine fibroids – 7,1% (n=2), which required expanding the scope of the operation to hysterectomy without appendages. In 14,3% of cases, emergency CS was complicated by hypotonic bleeding (n=4). On the 5th-7th day after CS in 1 g the following were registered: postoperative suture infiltration (28,5%; n=8), colpitis (28,5%; n=8), endometritis (10,7%; n=3), uterine subinvolution (25%; n=7), endometritis with peritonitis (3,6%; n=1). Indications for planned CS: scar on uterus 86,2% (n=369), breech presentation 38,8% (n=38), placenta previa 4,6% (n=20), symphysitis 0,2% (n=1). In 2 gr-5 complications (1,2%): uterine subinvolution (n=4), postoperative suture infiltration (n=1). Analysis of the anamnesis of women with complicated childbirth by CS showed that in all cases there were inflammatory diseases of the genital organs, pregnancy proceeded against the background of threatened miscarriage (60,6%), gestosis (36,3%), with abnormalities of placenta attachment (9,1%).

The main causes of purulent-septic complications are foci of chronic infection: pyelonephritis (36,3%), carious teeth (91%), tonsillitis (15,1%), as well as signs

of infection during real pregnancy: ARVI (75,3%), appendicitis (3%). Thus, the frequency of complications after an emergency CS significantly exceeds that after a planned CS, which dictates the need reducing this indicator by strengthening control during pregnancy management at the stage of antenatal consultation with mandatory prenatal hospitalization for high-risk pregnant women.

